

Does TRPA1 Activity Affect the Operating Point of the Organ of Corti After Noise Exposure?

Samantha A. Radomski¹, D. Susana Llanes-Coronel¹ and A. Catalina Vélez-Ortega^{1, a)}

¹*Department of Physiology, University of Kentucky, Lexington, KY, USA.*

^{a)}*Corresponding author: catavelezo@uky.edu*

Abstract. TRPA1 channels are master sensors of tissue damage. We recently showed that, after acoustic trauma, TRPA1 activation in cochlear supporting cells regulates hearing sensitivity and is a component of the temporary threshold shift (TTS). Our *ex vivo* findings showed that TRPA1 activation in the Hensen's cells leads to prolonged calcium responses that propagate across the organ of Corti and cause long-lasting tissue displacements. In *vivo*, such shape changes in the nonsensory supporting cells would be expected to affect the geometry and/or stiffness of the cochlear partition and, consequently, cochlear amplification. Consistent with this hypothesis, five days after noise exposure (which leads to the generation of TRPA1 agonists in the cochlear epithelium), wild-type mice exhibited smaller distortion-product otoacoustic emissions and higher auditory brainstem response (ABR) thresholds when compared to littermates deficient in TRPA1 (*Trpa1*^{-/-}). These results indicate that TRPA1 activity is a component of the noise-induced TTS. However, we still do not have direct evidence of TRPA1-mediated changes to the geometry and/or stiffness of the cochlear partition in adult mice. Here, we extracted cochlear microphonic (CM) data from ABR recordings to evaluate noise-induced changes in the operating point of the organ of Corti in the presence or absence of TRPA1. Our results show significant differences in the amplitude of the summing potential (SP) in click-evoked auditory brainstem responses between *Trpa1*^{-/-} mice and wild-type littermates. However, five days after a 30-minute exposure to broadband noise at 100 dB SPL, when both wild-type mice and *Trpa1*^{-/-} mice still exhibited elevated hearing thresholds, the SP differences were no longer observed due to an overall reduction in CM amplitudes in the *Trpa1*^{-/-} mice which was not seen in wild-type littermates. In addition, mice exhibited a direct current (DC) shift in the CM elicited by an 8 kHz tone burst as the sound intensity increased, which was delayed in *Trpa1*^{-/-} mice. Our results indicate that TRPA1 signaling during loud sound stimulation triggers a change in the operating point of outer hair cell mechanotransduction, which might serve as a protective mechanism to minimize noise induced tissue damage.

INTRODUCTION

The transient receptor potential cation channel A1 (TRPA1) is a non-selective cation channel expressed in somatosensory nociceptive neurons and in the inner ear [1-3]. TRPA1 channels are master sensors of tissue damage as they are gated and/or regulated by endogenous compounds generated upon tissue stress or injury (*e.g.*, extracellular ATP, low pH, pro-inflammatory prostaglandins, bradykinin, and byproducts of damage caused by reactive oxygen or nitrogen species) [4, 5]. In nociceptive neurons, these channels initiate somatic pain reflexes [6, 7]. In the inner ear, TRPA1-deficient (*Trpa1*^{-/-}) mice exhibit normal hearing, balance, and hair cell mechanotransduction [5-7], but our recent study shows that activation of TRPA1 channels contributes to the temporary shift of hearing thresholds (TTS) [5]. In neonate mouse cochlear explants, we found that TRPA1 signaling induces changes in the shape of several supporting cells. In the adult organ of Corti, these cell shape changes might impact the stiffness and/or geometry of the cochlear partition and thus modify the cochlear amplification mediated by outer hair cell (OHC) electromotility. Since noise exposure leads to the accumulation of 4-HNE in the cochlea [8] and 4-HNE is a potent TRPA1 ligand [9], we hypothesized that noise exposure would lead to the activation of TRPA1 channels and to subsequent changes in cochlear amplification. In agreement with our hypothesis, after moderate noise exposure (100 dB SPL broadband noise for 30 min) wild-type mice exhibited a longer reduction in distortion product otoacoustic emissions (DPOAE) (*i.e.* reduced cochlear amplification) and longer elevation of hearing thresholds (*i.e.* longer TTS, assessed via auditory brainstem responses, ABR) than *Trpa1*^{-/-} mice [5]. In addition, noise exposure led to permanent changes in ABR waveforms in *Trpa1*^{-/-} mice but not in wild-type littermates [5], which could indicate permanent cochlear damage.

Therefore, TRPA1 signaling might provide a mechanism of protection against permanent noise-induced tissue damage. Lastly, we showed that TRPA1 agonists can induce calcium waves and cell shape changes in the supporting cells of the cochlear epithelium of young adult mice (postnatal days 19-21) [5]. While these TRPA1-driven changes to the geometry of the organ of Corti were easily assessed in the neonate tissue, we were unable to evaluate whether TRPA1 activation induces changes to the morphology of the cochlear partition in adult mice. Here, we used ABR recordings to extract summing potential (SP) and cochlear microphonic (CM) data in the same mice, before and after noise exposure, as a proxy for the detection of noise-induced changes to the morphology of the cochlear partition in *Trpa1*^{-/-} mice and wild-type littermates.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Mice

We used the *Trpa1*^{-/-} mice generated by Dr. Kwan and Dr. Corey [7] which are maintained in a C57Bl/6 background in our laboratory, and *Cib2*^{F91S/F91S} mice generated by Dr. Zubair Ahmed [10] were kindly provided to us by Dr. Gregory Frolenkov. Ratios of roughly 50:50 male:female mice were used in all experiments. No significant differences in mouse body weight were observed between genotypes (18.3 ± 3.3 g vs. 18.8 ± 3.3 g for wild-type and *Trpa1*^{-/-} mice, $P = 0.7$, two-sided Student's *t* test). All animal procedures were approved by the University of Kentucky Animal Care and Use Committee (protocol 2020-3535).

Auditory Brainstem Responses and Cochlear Microphonics

Young adult (5-week-old) mice were used in all experiments. Mice were anesthetized with intraperitoneal injections of 2,2,2-tribromoethanol (Avertin) at 0.44 mg/g of body weight. Auditory brainstem responses (ABRs) were measured using the System 3 Auditory Workstation and BioSigRP software (Tucker-Davis Technologies). Click stimuli (33 μ s) with alternating polarity were presented at 20 Hz and signals from subdermal electrodes were collected at a frame rate of 50 kHz, high pass (HP) filtered at 300 Hz, low pass (LP) filtered at 7 kHz, and averaged 750 times to reveal ABRs. To extract cochlear microphonics (CM), 8 kHz tone bursts (3 ms) at 100 dB SPL (gated on and off with a Blackman gating function) were presented at 0° phase for 500 recordings (50 kHz frame rate, filtered at 300 Hz HP and 10 kHz LP) followed immediately by tone bursts at 180° phase for additional 500 recordings. The 0° and 180° phase recordings were averaged to obtain ABRs and subtracted to obtain CM (Fig. 1A). ABRs were obtained before and after exposure to broadband (white) noise at 100 dB SPL for 30 min. All stimuli were presented through an MF-1 speaker (Tucker-Davis Technologies). With this approach we obtained CM recordings in live mice that were significantly larger than those recorded in post-mortem mice or live mice lacking hair cell mechanotransduction (*Cib2*^{F91S/F91S}) (Fig. 1B). Quantifications of multiple CM recordings in the same mice over multiple days yielded a variability in CM maximum amplitude of $\pm 0.65 \mu$ V ($n = 7$).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TRPA1-Mediated Differences in the Amplitude of the Summing Potential are Affected by Noise Exposure

To assess whether TRPA1 signaling leads to changes in the geometry of the organ of Corti after noise exposure, we first evaluated changes to the amplitude of the click-evoked SP in *Trpa1*^{-/-} mice and wild-type littermates before and five days after exposure to moderate noise. Similar to our previous findings [5], exposure to white noise at 100 dB SPL for 30 min led to a significant elevation of hearing thresholds, when assessed via click-evoked ABR (Fig. 2a). Five days after noise exposure, the hearing thresholds had significantly recovered but still remained elevated from baseline levels in both *Trpa1*^{-/-} mice (47.67 ± 3.7 dB SPL before vs. 50.67 ± 5.3 dB SPL 5 days after, paired *t* test, $P = 0.045$) and wild-type mice (46.33 ± 4.0 dB SPL before vs. 53.0 ± 11.6 dB SPL 5 days after, paired *t* test, $P = 0.048$) (Fig. 2a). With the same noise exposure paradigm, we previously showed a faster recovery in hearing thresholds in

Trpa1^{-/-} mice with differences in magnitude depending on the frequency of sound stimulation, but these differences are harder to appreciate in response to click stimuli ([5] and Fig. 2a). Even though the ABR hearing thresholds to click stimuli were indistinguishable between *Trpa1*^{-/-} and wild-type mice before noise exposure (Fig. 2a), measurements of the SP revealed a significantly higher SP amplitude in *Trpa1*^{-/-} mice (Fig. 2b left). This difference, however, was no longer present five days after the exposure to moderate noise (Fig. 2b right).

FIGURE 1. (a) Representative auditory brainstem response (ABR) waveforms to 8 kHz stimuli at 100 dB SPL presented at either 0° (green) or 180° (purple) phase. Both recordings were averaged to obtain a typical ABR waveform (black), or subtracted to obtain the cochlear microphonics (CM, blue). Only the 0° phase of the 8 kHz stimulus (orange) is shown. (b) Maximum amplitudes of CM in live (dark blue) and in post-mortem or live *Cib2*^{F915/F915} mice (light blue) mice in response to an 8 kHz tone burst with increasing intensities from 30 to 110 dB SPL. Data are shown as mean ± S.D. Asterisks indicate statistical significance at specific tone intensities (Student's *t* test) or between groups (two-way ANOVA): **P*<0.05, ***P*<0.01, *****P*<0.0001.

FIGURE 2. (a) Hearing thresholds in wild-type (black) and *Trpa1*^{-/-} (red) mice determined with click-evoked ABR before and two timepoints after exposure to white noise at 100 dB SPL for 30 min. (b) Summating potential amplitudes (as indicated in inset cartoon) in click-evoked ABR before noise exposure and after 5 days of recovery in wild-type (black) and *Trpa1*^{-/-} (red) mice. Data are shown as mean ± S.E.M. Asterisks indicate statistical significance at time points after noise exposure vs. baseline values (paired *t* test) or between genotypes (two-way ANOVA): **P*<0.05, ***P*<0.01, *****P*<0.0001, n.s. not significant.

TRPA1-Deficient Mice Exhibit a Noise-Induced Reduction in Amplitude of the Cochlear Microphonics

In addition to obtaining click evoked ABRs, we also recorded the ABR evoked by an 8 kHz tone burst in each mouse before and five days after noise exposure. We recorded the ABR responses to tone bursts presented at 0° and 180° separately to gain access to CM responses (Fig. 1). Before noise exposure, the maximum amplitude of the CM was similar between the *Trpa1*^{-/-} mice and wild-type littermates ($3.30 \pm 1.16 \mu\text{V}$ vs. $2.91 \pm 1.31 \mu\text{V}$, respectively, two-sided Student's *t* test, $P = 0.42$). In addition, five days after the noise exposure, there were no significant changes in the average maximum amplitude of CM in wild-type mice (Fig. 3). However, some mice did show large increases or decreases in their CM maximum amplitude that were larger than our previously measured experimental variability. Interestingly, the majority of these mice were female thus we are currently exploring gender differences in TRPA1 signaling. In contrast, in *Trpa1*^{-/-} mice (male and female), the overall maximum amplitude of CM significantly decreased five days after noise exposure in most of the animals (Fig. 3). This significant decrease in CM amplitude after noise exposure in *Trpa1*^{-/-} but not in wild-type mice does not appear to be the result of elevated hearing thresholds. Therefore, there could be additional TRPA1-mediated mechanisms regulating sound-induced auditory nerve activity beyond the hypothesized changes to the operating point of the mechanotransduction machinery through changes in the shape of supporting cells.

FIGURE 3. Maximum amplitudes of CM (as indicated in inset cartoon) in wild-type (black) and *Trpa1*^{-/-} (red) mice in response to an 8 kHz tone burst with maximum intensity of 100 dB SPL. The CM amplitudes were measured before and 5 days after exposure to white noise at 100 dB SPL for 30 min. Asterisks indicate statistical significance (paired *t* test): ** $P < 0.01$, n.s. not significant.

TRPA1-Deficient Mice Exhibit a Delayed DC Shift in CM that is Altered After Noise Exposure

Before noise exposure, the CM in both *Trpa1*^{-/-} and wild-type mice appeared to reach saturation levels soon after stimulus onset (Fig. 4a *top*). However, five days after the exposure to noise, the rise and fall phases in CM amplitude were less steep (Fig. 4a *bottom*). Moreover, we observed an apparent direct-current (DC) shift in the CM of wild-type mice that started soon after the onset of the 8 kHz tone burst continuing roughly until the peak of the stimulus (Fig. 4b). This DC shift in CM occurred similarly before the noise exposure and after five days of recovery. In contrast, *Trpa1*^{-/-} mice exhibited a delay of ~ 0.5 ms in the inflection point of the DC shift before noise exposure (Fig. 4b *top*) and appeared to lack a clear DC shift five days after the acoustic trauma (Fig. 4b *bottom*).

Our results indicate the presence of a TRPA1-mediated impact on CM responses before and after acoustic trauma. In the cochlear epithelium, TRPA1 channels are highly expressed in the Hensen's cells [1, 3], and TRPA1-mediated calcium responses can propagate from Hensen's cells to other supporting cells (Deiters' and pillar cells) [5] and may extend to hair cells where TRPA1-mediated inward currents were previously reported [11]. Hensen's cells are

electrically and chemically coupled to neighboring supporting cells through gap junctions [12]. Therefore, any TRPA1-mediated depolarizations in Hensen's cells could easily spread to Deiters' and pillar cells to modify cochlear geometry and impact cochlear responses [5, 13]. It is unknown whether there are molecular mechanisms in the organ of Corti that could allow for TRPA1 channel gating and/or TRPA1-mediated cell shape changes to occur within nanoseconds after stimulus onset, and that could explain the differences in the CM DC shift between wild-type and *Trpa1*^{-/-} mice that were observed before noise exposure. Alternatively, we previously showed that TRPA1 activation in the neonate organ of Corti leads to the release of ATP and subsequent activation of ATP-dependent calcium oscillations in the Kolliker's organ [5]. The Kolliker's organ consists of a cluster of supporting cells in the developing inner sulcus of the organ of Corti, and has been shown to be involved in the formation of the tectorial membrane and to spontaneously release ATP to extracellular fluids to aid in the proper innervation of the cochlea (reviewed in [14]). In addition, we showed that ATP can trigger TRPA1 channels downstream of P2Y signaling in HEK293 cells [5]. Therefore, the interplay between TRPA1 and ATP signaling pathways could be important for the proper development of the organ of Corti. Thus, we cannot rule out that mice that develop in the absence of TRPA1 signaling have different cochlear mechanical properties to those observed in wild-type mice. In contrast, any differences observed in SP and CM between wild-type and *Trpa1*^{-/-} mice five days after the acoustic trauma could be consistent with an activation of TRPA1 channels due to the accumulation of reactive oxygen damage in the cochlear epithelium [5, 8].

FIGURE 4. Amplitude (a) and DC shift (b) of the CM in wild-type (black) and *Trpa1*^{-/-} (red) mice in response to an 8 kHz tone burst with maximum intensity of 100 dB SPL (orange). The CM was measured before (top traces) and 5 days after (middle traces) exposure to white noise at 100 dB SPL for 30 min. CM traces show the mean (thick line) ± S.E.M. (shaded area). The arrows indicate the inflection points where the DC shifts in the CM begin for wild-type (gray) and *Trpa1*^{-/-} (pink) mice.

Further explorations of changes in SP and CM in the presence or absence of TRPA1 are required to fully elucidate the TRPA1-dependent mechanisms regulating cochlear amplification after noise exposure. In fact, the larger differences in hearing thresholds and distortion product otoacoustic emissions (DPOAE) were previously observed after stimulation with higher sound frequencies (e.g., 16 kHz) than those utilized here (i.e. 8 kHz). Nevertheless, the differences observed here after 8 kHz tone burst stimulation highlight the validity of CM recordings to uncover changes in cochlear mechanics that were previously unappreciated.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was partially supported by intramural REACH funds from the College of Medicine and the Department of Physiology at the University of Kentucky.

REFERENCES

1. D.P. Corey, J. Garcia-Anoveros, J.R. Holt, K.Y. Kwan, S.Y. Lin, M.A. Vollrath, A. Amalfitano, E.L. Cheung, B.H. Derfler, A. Duggan, G.S. Geleoc, P.A. Gray, M.P. Hoffman, H.L. Rehm, D. Tamasauskas, and D.S. Zhang, "TRPA1 is a candidate for the mechanosensitive transduction channel of vertebrate hair cells", in *Nature*, (2004). 432(7018): p. 723-30.
2. G.M. Story, A.M. Peier, A.J. Reeve, S.R. Eid, J. Mosbacher, T.R. Hricik, T.J. Earley, A.C. Hergarden, D.A. Andersson, S.W. Hwang, P. McIntyre, T. Jegla, S. Bevan, and A. Patapoutian, "ANKTM1, a TRP-like channel expressed in nociceptive neurons, is activated by cold temperatures", in *Cell*, (2003). 112(6): p. 819-29.
3. M.J. Patil, S.H. Kim, P.K. Bahia, S.S. Nair, T.S. Darcey, J. Fiallo, X.X. Zhu, R.D. Frisina, S.H. Hadley, and T.E. Taylor-Clark, "A Novel Flp Reporter Mouse Shows That TRPA1 Expression Is Largely Limited to Sensory Neuron Subsets", in *eNeuro*, (2023). 10(12)
4. D.M. Bautista, M. Pellegrino, and M. Tsunozaki, "TRPA1: A gatekeeper for inflammation", in *Annu Rev Physiol*, (2013). 75: p. 181-200.
5. A.C. Velez-Ortega, R. Stepanyan, S.E. Edelman, S. Torres-Gallego, C. Park, D.A. Marinkova, J.S. Nowacki, G.P. Sinha, and G.I. Frolenkov, "TRPA1 activation in non-sensory supporting cells contributes to regulation of cochlear sensitivity after acoustic trauma", in *Nat Commun*, (2023). 14(1): p. 3871.
6. D.M. Bautista, S.E. Jordt, T. Nikai, P.R. Tsuruda, A.J. Read, J. Poblete, E.N. Yamoah, A.I. Basbaum, and D. Julius, "TRPA1 mediates the inflammatory actions of environmental irritants and proalgesic agents", in *Cell*, (2006). 124(6): p. 1269-82.
7. K.Y. Kwan, A.J. Allchorne, M.A. Vollrath, A.P. Christensen, D.S. Zhang, C.J. Woolf, and D.P. Corey, "TRPA1 contributes to cold, mechanical, and chemical nociception but is not essential for hair-cell transduction", in *Neuron*, (2006). 50(2): p. 277-89.
8. D. Yamashita, H.Y. Jiang, J. Schacht, and J.M. Miller, "Delayed production of free radicals following noise exposure", in *Brain Res*, (2004). 1019(1-2): p. 201-9.
9. M. Trevisani, J. Siemens, S. Materazzi, D.M. Bautista, R. Nassini, B. Campi, N. Imamachi, E. Andre, R. Patacchini, G.S. Cottrell, R. Gatti, A.I. Basbaum, N.W. Bunnnett, D. Julius, and P. Geppetti, "4-Hydroxynonenal, an endogenous aldehyde, causes pain and neurogenic inflammation through activation of the irritant receptor TRPA1", in *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, (2007). 104(33): p. 13519-24.
10. A.P.J. Giese, Y.Q. Tang, G.P. Sinha, M.R. Bowl, A.C. Goldring, A. Parker, M.J. Freeman, S.D.M. Brown, S. Riazuddin, R. Fettiplace, W.R. Schafer, G.I. Frolenkov, and Z.M. Ahmed, "CIB2 interacts with TMC1 and TMC2 and is essential for mechanotransduction in auditory hair cells", in *Nat Commun*, (2017). 8(1): p. 43.
11. R.S. Stepanyan, A.A. Indzhykulian, A.C. Velez-Ortega, E.T. Boger, P.S. Steyger, T.B. Friedman, and G.I. Frolenkov, "TRPA1-mediated accumulation of aminoglycosides in mouse cochlear outer hair cells", in *J Assoc Res Otolaryngol*, (2011). 12(6): p. 729-40.
12. D.J. Jagger and A. Forge, "Compartmentalized and signal-selective gap junctional coupling in the hearing cochlea", in *J Neurosci*, (2006). 26(4): p. 1260-8.
13. V.A. Lukashkina, S. Levic, P. Simoes, Z. Xu, J.A. DiGuseppi, J. Zuo, A.N. Lukashin, and I.J. Russell, "In Vivo Optogenetics Reveals Control of Cochlear Electromechanical Responses by Supporting Cells", in *J Neurosci*, (2022). 42(29): p. 5660-5671.
14. J. Chen, D. Gao, L. Sun, and J. Yang, "Kolliker's organ-supporting cells and cochlear auditory development", in *Front Mol Neurosci*, (2022). 15: p. 1031989.

Comments and Discussion

1. **[Philip Hehlert]:** If TRPA1 signaling during loud sound stimulation alters the operating point of OHC mechanotransduction, can this effect be suppressed by TRPA1-inhibitors?

[S. A. Radomski and A. C. Velez-Ortega]: We are planning to test this in a future experiment. We will measure ABR and CM in wild-type mice before and after the application of a TRPA1 antagonist.

2. **[Philip Hehlert]:** Consequently, are TRPA1-stimulated mice exhibiting more sensitivity to loud stimuli?

[S. A. Radomski and A. C. Velez-Ortega]: Unfortunately, application of TRPA1 agonists to mice would induce too many side effects since TRPA1 activation would cause severe pain. However, there is a human family that carries a gain-of-function mutation in the *TRPA1* gene and we are about to start performing several hearing tests on members of this family to evaluate the effect of increased TRPA1 activity on their auditory function.

3. **[Philip Hehlert]:** Is it possible to investigate what the effects are on a higher frequency like 16 kHz?

[S. A. Radomski and A. C. Velez-Ortega]: Yes, this is possible. The reason 8 kHz was the only frequency investigated here was due to hardware limitations. We are in the process of setting up a new hardware configuration to test a wider range of frequencies, including 16 kHz.

4. **[Philip Hehlert]:** Could the authors elaborate on the CM-amplitudes of particularly *Trpa1*^{+/+} that are elevated 5 days after noise (30% of animals showed this) in the discussion?

[S. A. Radomski and A. C. Velez-Ortega]: We greatly appreciate this question. We have added the typical differences we observe between multiple CM measurements in the same animal over different days as a reference of our experimental variability. We initially thought these changes were within this experimental variability. However, further examination revealed that some of the wild-type mice had noise-induced changes to their the overall changes in CM maximum amplitude observed in the TRPA1-deficient mice may not be explained by such experimental variability.

5. **[Philip Hehlert]:** Are you planning to measure altered mechanics of the organ of Corti directly and/or quantify geometric changes in TRPA1-mice?

[S. A. Radomski and A. C. Velez-Ortega]: It is definitely one of our goals! We are hoping to collaborate with another research group to perform optical coherence tomography (OCT) in wild-type and *Trpa1*^{-/-} mice, either with or without noise exposure.